

Exact Diagonalization Study of Quantum Spin Systems

M.Sc. Project - Stage II

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by

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Chapter 1

MAJUMDAR-GHOSH MODEL

1.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

$S = 1/2$ Heisenberg chain exhibits interesting phenomenon like quantum phase transition when a next-nearest-neighbour interaction is included in the hamiltonian.

$$H = J_1 \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1} + J_2 \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+2} \quad (1.1)$$

This model is named J_1 - J_2 chain or the Majumdar-Ghosh model and here a part of the most well understood transition which takes place when both J_1 and J_2 are antiferromagnetic, has been discussed in short.

1.2 COMPUTATIONAL METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

Exact Diagonalization technique has been employed for analysing the systems. This method has severe limitations as Hilbert space size scales as 2^N for a Spin-1/2 system (N is the number of spins). Our study has been limited to 16 spins on a chain. To reduce the exact diagonalization cost block diagonalization has been used here. J_1 - J_2 chain conserves m_z magnetization and shows Translation symmetry. These symmetries result in block diagonalization of the whole hamiltonian.

In our study, first m_z symmetry was employed and then each m_z block was further divided into smaller blocks using Translational symmetry.

After diagonalization of a particular momentum block, all energies were tagged with the corresponding k-value and stored. Later using this list of energy, degeneracy was calculated for each energy to determine the total spin S . After that energies were sorted out based on their corresponding k and S value.

1.3 RESULT

Figure 1.1. Phase Transition in 1D Majumdar-Ghosh Chain. J_1 is the strength of first-nearest neighbour interaction and J_2 is the strength of second nearest-neighbour interaction.

1.4 DISCUSSION

As can be seen from the plots, ground state is always a singlet ($S = 0$). For chain of size $L = 4n$, the ground state has momentum $k = 0$; it is a fully symmetric singlet state. But for $L = 4n + 2$, the ground state has momentum $k = \pi$; it is an anti-symmetric singlet state.

If g is defined as J_2/J_1 , for $g < g_{cross}$, $g_{cross} \approx 0.25$, the system is in the same phase as the Heisenberg chain ($J_2 = 0$) where triplet ($S = 1$) is the first excited state with $k = 0$ for $L = 4n + 2$ (and $k = \pi$ for $L = 4n$). At $g \approx 0.25$, $k = 0$ for $L = 4n + 2$ (and $k = \pi$ for $L = 4n$) singlet and triplet excited levels cross each other; singlet level becomes lower in energy than triplet level. Both singlet levels become degenerate at $g \approx 0.5$. This crossing point g_{cross} can be used as critical (dimerization) coupling g_c .

On a even ring and at the special point $g = 1/2$ (Majumdar-Ghosh point), the ground state is a two-fold degenerate singlet product. These degenerate states $|\Psi_A\rangle$ and $|\Psi_B\rangle$ break translational symmetry and can form one symmetric state that has momentum $k = 0$ and one anti-symmetric state that has momentum $k = \pi$:^[1]

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = (|\Psi_A\rangle + |\Psi_B\rangle)/\sqrt{2}, \quad |\Psi(\pi)\rangle = (|\Psi_A\rangle - |\Psi_B\rangle)/\sqrt{2} \quad (1.2)$$

Figure 1.2. Degenerate ground states at the Majumdar-Ghosh point. The thick red arcs show singlets; At $g = 1/2$ the product of these singlets on alternating bonds is an exact ground state.^[1]

At $g = 1/2$, both of the symmetric and anti-symmetric singlet states become degenerate ground state of the periodic chain; as can be seen in the plots. As system size grows and more frustration are added in the system due to increased no. of J_2 interactions, gap between singlet ground state and singlet excited state decreases.

Chapter 2

SPIN-1 HONEYCOMB MAGNET

2.1 MOTIVATION

Recent Experimental studies have shown that single-ion anisotropy and frustration play a crucial role in determining the phases of Spin-1 Honeycomb Lattices. The experimental outcome indicated a disordered system with certain types of interactions with certain strengths, between spins present in the lattice.^[2] This project aims to computationally study such a system to look for any finding that can potentially come in agreement with the experimental results.

Spin-1 magnets have numerous applications in fields like Spintronics, Quantum Computing and Magnetic Materials Research.^[1] The honeycomb structure can be exploited to create devices like spin valves, spin filters and magnetic tunnel junctions for efficient data storage and processing in electronics. Decoherence, a common issue in quantum computing, can be solved with stable qubits supported by properties of Honeycomb systems as they are less susceptible to decoherence.^[3] Configurable spin configurations are highly valuable for enhancing data storage density and bolstering data retention in magnetic storage devices constructed with such lattice systems. Spin-1 Honeycomb Magnets are effective systems for understanding fundamental magnetic properties and interactions. Also, the exhibition of topological properties makes them suitable for studying topological insulators and related phenomena.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL BACKGROUNDS

A recent experimental study done on $Cu_3LiRu_2O_6$ ($Ru^{4+} 4d^4$ on Honeycomb Lattice) suggested that a Quantum Spin Liquid realization may be possible in the honeycomb system.^[4] Experimental findings follow as - the first nearest-neighbour interaction is Antiferromagnetic with strength $J_1 = -18.1 meV$, second nearest-neighbour interaction is Ferromagnetic with strength $J_2 = 1 meV$ and the third nearest-neighbour interaction is also Ferromagnetic with strength $J_3 = 11.5 meV$ which is approximately 2/3 of J_1 . Spin-orbit coupling induced Anisotropy is also present in the lattice system. It has been estimated that anisotropy and frustrated couplings are leading to a spin-orbital liquid.

2.3 SINGLE ION ANISOTROPY

In the study of magnetic materials, the interaction between individual magnetic ions and their surrounding lattice plays a crucial role in determining the material's magnetic properties. One significant aspect of this interaction is single ion anisotropy, which describes the preferred orientation of a magnetic moment of an individual ion relative to a specific direction within the lattice. In this project, the implications of single ion anisotropy within a honeycomb lattice have been investigated, focusing on its effect on the behaviour of the system.^[5]

The Hamiltonian of a magnetic system encompasses various terms that capture the interactions between magnetic moments. One such term is the single ion anisotropy term, often denoted as H_{aniso} , which accounts for the energy associated with aligning the magnetic moment along a preferred axis or easy axis. Within a honeycomb lattice, this term can be expressed as:

$$H_{\text{aniso}} = D \sum_i (\hat{S}_i \cdot \hat{n}_i)^2 \quad (2.1)$$

Here, D represents the single ion anisotropy constant, \sum_i denotes the summation over all magnetic ions in the lattice, \hat{S}_i is the unit vector for the magnetic moment of the i -th ion, and \hat{n}_i is the unit vector representing the preferred direction for that ion.^[6]

The single ion anisotropy term in the Hamiltonian influences the stability and behavior of magnetic configurations within the honeycomb lattice. In this case, the energy is minimized when the magnetic moment of each ion aligns antiparallel to the preferred direction or easy axis \hat{n}_i . This behavior is characteristic of an antiferromagnetic-like system.

2.4 FRUSTRATION

Frustration in magnetic systems arises when competing interactions prevent the system from achieving a single, globally optimal magnetic configuration.^[7] One of the classic examples of frustration occurs in the honeycomb lattice, where the geometric arrangement of magnetic moments leads to intricate magnetic behaviors.^[8] In this report, we will explore into the concept of frustration in honeycomb lattices and its effect on magnetic properties.

The frustration in a honeycomb lattice stems from the competition between different types of magnetic interactions. For instance, antiferromagnetic interactions between neighboring spins may conflict with ferromagnetic interactions in certain directions. This competition results in frustration as the system cannot simultaneously minimize all interaction energies.

2.5 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Hamiltonian of the honeycomb system in our study has been taken as,

$$H = J_1 \sum_i \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1} + J_3 \sum_i \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+3} + D \sum_i (\hat{S}_i^z)^2 \quad (2.2)$$

Where J_1 term is the nearest-neighbour Heisenberg interaction and J_3 term is the third nearest-neighbour Heisenberg interaction. D term signifies the single-ion anisotropy.^[9]

D is positive throughout our study but we have taken all possible combinations between J_1 and J_3 terms. When the first nearest-neighbour interaction is Antiferromagnetic, the third nearest-neighbour interaction has been taken as both Antiferromagnetic and Ferromagnetic separately. Similarly, when J_1 term is Ferromagnetic, J_3 term has been taken as both Ferromagnetic and Antiferromagnetic to study the effects on the behaviour of the lattice.

2.6 RELEVANT ORDER PARAMETERS

Three order parameters have been computed for the honeycomb system in our study; Magnetization (M_z) for ferromagnetic J_1 , Staggered Magnetization (M_z^{stg}) in case of antiferromagnetic J_1 and the other one is Spin Nematic Order (Q_{zz}). Total magnetization (per site) is:

$$M_z = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N m_i^z \quad (2.3)$$

Staggered magnetization (per site) is defined as:

$$M_z^{stg} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i m_i^z \quad (2.4)$$

where $\phi_i = \pm 1$ is the staggered phase factor; on the honeycomb lattice the sign of m_z magnetization changes within the unit cell, so ϕ_i can be taken as 1 when i is even and -1 when i is odd.

Per site Spin Nematic order is defined as:

$$Q_{zz} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[(m_i^z)^2 - \frac{2}{3} \right] \quad (2.5)$$

2.7 COMPUTATIONAL METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

Exact Diagonalization technique has been employed for studying and analysing the systems. This method has severe limitations as Hilbert space size scales as 3^N for a Spin-1 system (N is the number of spins). The computations have to be limited to small-sized lattices and we could not reach beyond 12 spins (3×2 lattice). From the Energy diagrams, it has been concluded that the ground state always lies in the $m_z = 0$ sector. As we were interested only in the ground state, we got the advantage of restricting our numerical analysis only in the $m_z = 0$ sector with a smaller Hilbert space. 2×2 lattice (8 spins) comprises of 1107 basis states and 3×2 lattice (12 spins) comprises of 73789 basis states in $m_z = 0$ sector.

The sparsity of the Hamiltonian matrices made the computation relatively less time-consuming. To enhance the efficiency, Hamiltonian matrices corresponding to J_1 , J_3 , and D were generated separately and stored accordingly. Some relevant magnetic order parameters have been computed in the ground state and our focus was on trying to track any kind of phase transition. Order parameters and Energies have been plotted against the varying ratio D/J_1 and for different values of J_3 to monitor the behaviour of the parameters J_1 has been scaled to either 1 (Antiferromagnetic interaction) or -1

(Ferromagnetic interaction) throughout the whole study. J_3 has been varied over a set of fractions of J_1 .

2.8 RESULTS

2.8.1 ANTIFERROMAGNETIC FIRST NEIGHBOUR INTERACTION

1. No Third Neighbour Interaction

Figure 2.2. Energy Levels of Honeycomb lattice with only first neighbour interaction and Single Ion Anisotropy and no third nearest-neighbour interaction. D is Single Ion Anisotropy and J_1 is strength of first nearest-neighbour interaction.

Figure 2.3. Variation of average of square of Staggered Magnetization $\langle (M_z^{stg})^2 \rangle$ and average Nematic Order Parameter $\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$ with D/J_1 .

Figure 2.4. Variation of square root of average of square of Staggered Magnetization ($\langle (M_z^{stg})^2 \rangle$) and absolute value of average Nematic Order Parameter ($\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$) with D/J_1 . The crossing is around $D/J_1 = 2$.

Figure 2.5. Variation of ratio of Staggered Magnetization (M_z^{stg}) parameters, Binder ratio and ratio of Nematic Order (Q_{zz}) parameters with D/J_1 . Binder ratio crosses Nematic order parameters ratio at around $D/J_1 = 2.5$.

2. Frustrating Third Neighbour Interaction

Figure 2.6. Energy Levels of Honeycomb lattice with frustrating third nearest-neighbour interaction of different strength. D is Single Ion Anisotropy, J_1 is the strength of first nearest-neighbour interaction and J_3 is strength of third nearest-neighbour interaction.

Figure 2.7. Variation of average of square of Staggered Magnetization $((M_z^{stg})^2)$ and average Nematic Order Parameter (Q_{zz}) with D/J_1 for frustrating third nearest-neighbour interaction (J_3) of different strength.

Figure 2.8. Variation of square root of average of square of Staggered Magnetization ($\langle (M_z^{stg})^2 \rangle$) and absolute value of average Nematic Order Parameter ($\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$) with D/J_1 . The crossing varies in between $D/J_1 = 1$ to $D/J_1 = 1.5$.

Figure 2.9. Variation of ratio of Staggered Magnetization (M_z^{stg}) parameters, Binder ratio and ratio of Nematic Order (Q_{zz}) parameters with D/J_1 . Crossing of Binder ratio and Nematic order parameters varies in between $D/J_1 = 1.5$ to $D/J_1 = 2$.

3. Non-Frustrating Third Neighbour Interaction

Figure 2.10. Energy Levels of Honeycomb lattice with non-frustrating third nearest-neighbour interaction of different strength. D is Single Ion Anisotropy, J_1 is the strength of first nearest-neighbour interaction and J_3 is strength of third nearest-neighbour interaction.

Figure 2.11. Variation of average of square of Staggered Magnetization $((M_z^{stg})^2)$ and average Nematic Order Parameter (Q_{zz}) with D/J_1 for non-frustrating third nearest-neighbour interaction (J_3) of different strength.

Figure 2.12. Variation of square root of average of square of Staggered Magnetization ($\langle (M_z^{stg})^2 \rangle$) and absolute value of average Nematic Order Parameter ($\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$) with D/J_1 . The crossing varies in between $D/J_1 = 2$ to $D/J_1 = 2.5$.

Figure 2.13. Variation of ratio of Staggered Magnetization (M_z^{stg}) parameters, Binder ratio and ratio of Nematic Order (Q_{zz}) parameters with D/J_1 . Crossing of Binder ratio and Nematic order parameters ratio varies in between $D/J_1 = 2.5$ to $D/J_1 = 4.5$.

2.8.2 FERROMAGNETIC FIRST NEIGHBOUR INTERACTION

1. No Third Neighbour Interaction

Figure 2.14. Energy Levels of Honeycomb lattice with only first neighbour interaction and Single Ion Anisotropy and no third nearest-neighbour interaction. D is Single Ion Anisotropy and J_1 is strength of first nearest-neighbour interaction.

Figure 2.15. Variation of average of square of Magnetization $\langle (M_z)^2 \rangle$ and average Nematic Order Parameter $\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$ with D/J_1 .

Figure 2.16. Variation of square root of average of square of Magnetization ($\langle (M_z)^2 \rangle$) and absolute value of average Nematic Order Parameter (Q_{zz}) with D/J_1 . The crossing is around $|D/J_1| = 0.5$.

Figure 2.17. Variation of ratio of Magnetization (M_z) parameters, Binder ratio and ratio of Nematic Order (Q_{zz}) parameters with D/J_1 . Binder ratio crosses Nematic order parameters ratio at around $|D/J_1| = 2$.

2. Frustrating Third Neighbour Interaction

Figure 2.18. Energy Levels of Honeycomb lattice with frustrating third nearest-neighbour interaction of different strength. D is Single Ion Anisotropy, J_1 is the strength of first nearest-neighbour interaction and J_3 is strength of third nearest-neighbour interaction.

Figure 2.19. Variation of average of square of Magnetization $\langle (M_z)^2 \rangle$ and average Nematic Order Parameter $\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$ with D/J_1 for frustrating third nearest-neighbour interaction (J_3) of different strength.

Figure 2.20. Variation of square root of average of square of Magnetization ($\langle (M_z)^2 \rangle$) and absolute value of average Nematic Order Parameter (Q_{zz}) with D/J_1 . The crossing varies in between $|D/J_1| = 0.5$ to $|D/J_1| = 1$.

Figure 2.21. Variation of ratio of Magnetization (M_z) parameters, Binder ratio and ratio of Nematic Order (Q_{zz}) parameters with D/J_1 . Crossing of Binder ratio and Nematic order parameters ratio varies in between $|D/J_1| = 1$ to $|D/J_1| = 2$.

3. Non-Frustrating Third Neighbour Interaction

Figure 2.22. Energy Levels of Honeycomb lattice with non-frustrating third nearest-neighbour interaction of different strength. D is Single Ion Anisotropy, J_1 is the strength of first nearest-neighbour interaction and J_3 is strength of third nearest-neighbour interaction.

Figure 2.23. Variation of average of square of Magnetization $\langle (M_z)^2 \rangle$ and average Nematic Order Parameter $\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$ with D/J_1 for non-frustrating third nearest-neighbour interaction (J_3) of different strength.

Figure 2.24. Variation of square root of average of square of Magnetization ($\langle (M_z)^2 \rangle$) and absolute value of average Nematic Order Parameter (Q_{zz}) with D/J_1 . The crossing varies in between $|D/J_1| = 0.5$ to $|D/J_1| = 1$.

Figure 2.25. Variation of ratio of Magnetization (M_z) parameters, Binder ratio and ratio of Nematic Order (Q_{zz}) parameters with D/J_1 . Crossing of Binder ratio and Nematic order parameters ratio varies in between $|D/J_1| = 2$ to $|D/J_1| = 3.5$.

2.9 DISCUSSION

For antiferromagnetic first neighbour interaction; when no third neighbour interaction is present, ground state has $M_z = 0$ and energy levels become more closely spaced as system size grows. Average of square of staggered magnetization ($\langle(m_z^{stg})^2\rangle$) goes to zero and spin Nematic average ($\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$) goes to $-2/3$; this shows that average per site magnetization ($\langle m_z \rangle$) goes to zero as single ion anisotropy (D) dominates over J_1 . Crossing of $\sqrt{\langle(m_z^{stg})^2\rangle}$ and $|\langle Q_{zz} \rangle|$ is around $D/J_1 = 2$ and Binder ratio crosses Nematic order ratio at $D/J_1 \approx 2.5$. Hence it can be said that an antiferromagnetic to large- D phase transition is taking place at $D/J_1 \approx 2.5$.

Upon adding a frustrating third neighbour interaction (Ferromagnetic); energy decreases and energy levels come closer as J_3 interaction gets stronger. The $|\langle Q_{zz} \rangle|$ crossing varies from $D/J_1 = 1.5$ to 1 and Binder ratio crossing varies from $D/J_1 = 2$ to 1.5 as J_3 increases.

In presence of a non-frustrating third neighbour interaction (Antiferromagnetic); the $|\langle Q_{zz} \rangle|$ crossing varies from $D/J_1 = 2$ to 2.5 and Binder ratio crossing varies from $D/J_1 = 2.5$ to 4.5 as J_3 increases. In this case non-frustrating J_3 interaction stabilizes the antiferromagnetic phase.^{[10][11]}

For ferromagnetic first neighbour interaction; when no third neighbour interaction is present, energy levels become more closely spaced as system size grows. Total M_z magnetization of the system is a $2N + 1$ multiplet (N is the number of spins) but ground state still has $M_z = 0$. Average of square of magnetization ($\langle(m_z)^2\rangle$) goes to zero and spin Nematic average ($\langle Q_{zz} \rangle$) saturates to $-2/3$; this implies that average per site magnetization (m_z) goes to zero as single ion anisotropy (D) dominates over J_1 . Crossing of $\sqrt{\langle(m_z)^2\rangle}$ and $|\langle Q_{zz} \rangle|$ is around $|D/J_1| = 0.5$ and Binder ratio crosses Nematic order ratio at $|D/J_1| \approx 2$. Hence it can be said that a multiplet- $M_z = 0$ phase to large- D phase transition is taking place at $|D/J_1| \approx 2$.

Upon adding a frustrating third neighbour interaction (Antiferromagnetic); energy per spin decreases. The $|\langle Q_{zz} \rangle|$ crossing point does not vary significantly; it moves from $|D/J_1| = 0.5$ to 1 but Binder ratio crossing varies from $|D/J_1| = 1$ to 2 as J_3 increases.

Also in presence of a non-frustrating third neighbour interaction (Ferromagnetic), $|\langle Q_{zz} \rangle|$ crossing point does not vary significantly; it stays around $|D/J_1| = 0.5$. Binder ratio crossing varies from $|D/J_1| = 2$ to 3.5 as J_3 interaction strengthens. Non-frustrating J_3 interaction stabilizes the multiplet- $M_z = 0$ phase.

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Phases of the J-Q Model

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Chapter 1

J-Q Model

1.1 Theoretical Framework

The J-Q Hamiltonian on a two-dimensional lattice is written as^[1]

$$H = -J \sum_{\langle ij \rangle} S_{ij} - Q \sum_{\langle ijkl \rangle} S_{ij} S_{kl} \quad (1.1)$$

In this model, the Heisenberg interaction equals a singlet projector operator S_{ij} with a constant shift: $H_{ij} = -S_{ij} + \frac{1}{4}$, and^[2]

$$S_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} - \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j \quad (1.2)$$

The singlet state for two sites, $|\phi_{ij}^s\rangle = \frac{|\uparrow_i \downarrow_j\rangle - |\downarrow_i \uparrow_j\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ is an eigenstate of this projector operator;

$$S_{ij} |\phi_{ij}^s\rangle = |\phi_{ij}^s\rangle, \quad S_{ij} |\phi_{ij}^{t,m}\rangle = 0, \quad (m = 0, \pm 1) \quad (1.3)$$

This property ensures that when S_{ij} acts on a superposition of singlet-triplet states, the triplet component is destroyed and only the singlet state is projected out. Thus formation of singlets on pairs of nearest-neighbor sites are favoured by this interaction. The J-Q class of models are built on the idea of projecting singlet bonds in a correlated manner, using products of several such S_{ij} operators on different bonds. This attempts to develop a higher density of short valence bonds, which can reduce or destroy antiferromagnetic ordering.^[1]

Figure 1.1. Singlet-projector operators S_{ij} . (a) is simply the Heisenberg interaction. (b) is the four-spin interaction among two bonds.^[1]

1.2 Relevant Order Parameters

To study the phase transition in J-Q model, computations have been done for spin-spin (C_s) and dimer-dimer (C_d) correlation functions,^[3]

$$\begin{aligned}
C_s(\mathbf{r}) &= \langle \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{0}) \cdot \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{r}) \rangle \\
C_d(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}) &= \langle [\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{0}) \cdot \mathbf{S}(\hat{\mathbf{x}})] [\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{r} + \hat{\mathbf{x}})] \rangle \\
C_d(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) &= \langle [\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{0}) \cdot \mathbf{S}(\hat{\mathbf{y}})] [\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{r} + \hat{\mathbf{y}})] \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{1.4}$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ denotes lattice unit vector in the x and y direction respectively. The AF order parameter is the staggered magnetization, the square of which is shown in the plot,

$$M^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{r}} C_s(\mathbf{r}) (-1)^{(r_x + r_y)} \tag{1.5}$$

The $\mathbf{q} = (\pi, 0)$ and $\mathbf{q} = (0, \pi)$ dimer order parameters are,

$$\begin{aligned}
D_x^2 &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{r}} C_d(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}) (-1)^{r_x} \\
D_y^2 &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{r}} C_d(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) (-1)^{r_y}
\end{aligned} \tag{1.6}$$

To detect Néel and VBS ordering, the following structure factors constructed out of the real-space correlators have been used:^[4]

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{q}) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'} e^{i(\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}') \cdot \mathbf{q}} \langle (\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{r}'}') \rangle \\
\mathcal{B}^\mu(\mathbf{q}) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'} e^{i(\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}') \cdot \mathbf{q}} \langle (\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{r}+\mathbf{e}_\mu}) (\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{r}'} \cdot \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{r}'+\mathbf{e}_\mu}) \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{1.7}$$

$\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{q})$ has been used to probe Néel order at the AFM ordering wave vector on the 2D lattice ((π, π) with lattice constants set to unity). The Néel correlation ratio R_N is defined as,

$$R_N \equiv \frac{R_{N_x} + R_{N_y}}{2} \quad (1.8)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} R_{N_x} &\equiv 1 - \frac{\mathcal{A}(\pi + \frac{2\pi}{L_x}, \pi)}{\mathcal{A}(\pi, \pi)} \\ R_{N_y} &\equiv 1 - \frac{\mathcal{A}(\pi, \pi + \frac{2\pi}{L_y})}{\mathcal{A}(\pi, \pi)} \end{aligned} \quad (1.9)$$

Similarly, $\mathcal{B}(\mathbf{q})$ is made out of bond-bond correlators and can be used to investigate VBS order at the ordering wave vector ($(\pi, 0)$ and $(0, \pi)$ with lattice constants set to unity). The VBS correlation ratio is defined as,

$$R_V \equiv \frac{R_{V_x} + R_{V_y}}{2} \quad (1.10)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} R_{V_x} &\equiv 1 - \frac{\mathcal{B}(\pi + \frac{2\pi}{L_x}, 0)}{\mathcal{B}(\pi, 0)} \\ R_{V_y} &\equiv 1 - \frac{\mathcal{B}(0, \pi + \frac{2\pi}{L_y})}{\mathcal{B}(0, \pi)} \end{aligned} \quad (1.11)$$

In presence of Néel order, R_N will nearly be 1 and R_V will nearly be zero, and vice-versa for VBS order. A combination of the parameters above are sufficient to study the Néel-VBS transitions.

1.3 Computational Methods and Techniques

Exact Diagonalization technique has been employed for studying and analysing the systems. This method has severe limitations as Hilbert space size scales as 2^N for a Spin-1/2 system (N is the number of spins). However, the J-Q Hamiltonian in (1.1) possesses SU(2) and U(1) symmetry, hence it conserves total Spin (S) and total magnetization M_z ($M_z = \sum_i m_i^z$). Also, for a lattice with periodic boundary condition, translational symmetry is present and momentum states can be constructed, which will result in a block diagonalization of the whole Hamiltonian matrix. Each such momentum block can

be further divided into two smaller blocks using Spin-inversion symmetry. Inversion symmetry is useful only in $M_z = 0$ sector and because of the antiferromagnetic nature of our model, the ground state and some low-lying excited states reside in the $M_z = 0$ sector. So, a symmetry resolved state would look like,^[1]

$$|a(M_z, k, z)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_a}} \sum_{r=0}^{N-1} e^{-ikr} T^r (1 + zZ) |a(M_z)\rangle \quad (1.12)$$

where T is translation operator, k is momentum, z is inversion quantum number and N_a is normalisation constant.

Computationally, N_a can be easily computed using $N_a = D_a |F_a(M_z, k, z)|^2$. D_a is the number of different states obtained among the group of $L_x \times L_y$ translations of the representative state $|a(M_z)\rangle$. A representative state is incompatible with the momentum k if the sum of phases $F_a(M_z, k, z)$ in over the translations bringing $|a(M_z)\rangle$ onto itself vanishes. The representative state has been chosen as the smallest equivalent decimal of all states (represented in binary) generated through translations of $|a(M_z)\rangle$.

1.4 Results

Figure 1.2. Energy levels with different momentum and total Spin in $M_z = 0$ sector for (a) 4×4 and (b) 6×4 lattice.

Figure 1.3. Staggered spin-spin correlation (M^2) and dimer-dimer correlation (D_x^2 and D_y^2) in the ground state of (a) 4×4 and (b) 6×4 lattice.

Figure 1.4. Néel correlation ratio (R_N) and VBS correlation ratio (R_V) in the ground state of (a) 4×4 and (b) 6×4 lattice.

1.5 Discussion

The ground state of J-Q model is a singlet and both the x momentum and y momentum are zero, as can be seen from Figure 1.2. The first excited state is a triplet and appear at (π, π) momentum. Interesting observation is: the singlet excitation at $(\pi, 0)$ momentum comes closer to the triplet excitation as strength of Q increases. The chief motivation of this study was to probe whether there happens to be a level crossing between singlet and triplet excitation at a critical Q , a scenario observed in the Majumdar-Ghosh model^[1]. It is evident that the aforementioned levels come closer and in larger lattice systems, it might demonstrate a scenario where the $(\pi, 0)$ singlet lowers its energy compared to the (π, π) triplet level. Unfortunately, ED calculations on (6×6) lattice could not be accessed due to some resource level issues.

Figure 1.3 shows that spin-spin correlation decreases and dimer-dimer correlation builds up as Q becomes stronger. This indicates the development of valence bonds. The variation of Néel and VBS correlation ratios confirm this behaviour (Figure 1.4). In low Q regime (1.1) is a Heisenberg model with a constant shift in energy; hence R_N is nearly 1, suggesting Néel ordering at (π, π) wave vector^[5,6,7]. On the other hand, VBS correlation ratio is initially near to zero but grows up with Q . However, from these small lattices it is not possible to determine a Q_c where Néel-VBS transition takes place in J-Q model.

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